

AMAP JMCS |
JOURNAL OF MEDIA AND COMMUNICATION
STUDIES

Volume 3, Issue 2. July 2023

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1234567

Website home: <https://jmcs.amcap.net/website>

Submission guidelines: <https://jmcs.amcap.net/website/page/submission-guidelines>

Date of Acceptance: 30/06/2023

Date of Publication: 10/07/2023

Article Title:

**Adoption Behavior towards Advance Broadcasting Technologies: A Critical
Study of PTV Sports**

Author(s):

Ahmed Raza

Lecturer at Department of Media & Communication Studies, University of Okara.

Email: ahmedraza92@outlook.com

Abstract

This study primarily focuses on the scale at which PTV Sports are adopting advance broadcasting technologies, and whether the management at PTV Sports are technologically conscious or not. In this research, it is analyzed that PTV Sports which has an incredible history, as it is associated to PTV that has achieved great feats in sports broadcasting in this region, why it is not able to incorporate modern broadcasting technologies the way it should have. Qualitative research method is applied in which in-depth interviews are conducted from a total of twelve experts, that are television sports broadcasters, sports journalists and transmission engineers from the PTV, PTV Sports and private television channels in Pakistan. Among these twelve, six are from PTV and PTV Sports, and the remaining six are associated to private television channels, keeping in view the prerequisites of this study. The communication theories of Diffusion of Innovation and Technological Determinism are applied to examine the data collected during this study. The outcome obtained after the data interpretation from the answers of interviewees suggest that the traditional mindset is not a major reason for PTV Sports not adopting advance broadcasting technologies, as it is corruption that has brought PTV to this disastrous stage the results of which are clearly visible in PTV Sports.

Keywords: *Adoption Behavior, Advance Broadcasting Technologies, PTV Sports, Traditional Mindset, Technologically Conscious*

Introduction

The relationship between sports and media goes back to the mid-18th century when newspapers began reporting sporting event results. This was clearly a win-win state for both parties. Newspapers secured new readers fascinated to the sports, while the sports organizations gained from the extra promotion that made their events more popular (Nitin Kumar PGPCM, 2003).

Fortunately, Pakistan is a country where exposure to the electronic media has deep roots. In this perspective, the Pakistan Television Corporation (abbreviated as PTV), which is Pakistan's first national television channel, began its transmission from Lahore on 26th November, 1964. President Ayub Khan inaugurated the first official television station of PTV in Lahore after an introduction by Syed Wajid Ali, the first-ever news broadcast which was beamed as a black and white transmission. Aslam Azhar who is widely considered to be the "father of Pakistan Television," was appointed the first Managing Director of Pakistan Television.

PTV was and still is renowned for delivering home entertainment which broadly can be categorized into two dimensions. The first one are the dramas, music programmes, documentaries, quiz shows, morning shows etc. The second one is the sports coverage. The second dimension, the sports coverage done by PTV made a significant impact not only in this region, but throughout the world. PTV right from its start gave huge importance to sports coverage, which is visible from the fact that after few years of its launch, PTV took the initiative of broadcasting live sports events played in Pakistan.

From 2000 onwards, the number of international sports events held in Pakistan reduced due to security reasons, and the attack on Sir Lanka cricket team bus in Lahore on 3rd March, 2009, almost took all the international sports events to be played within Pakistan. During this whole decade, PTV also faced a setback as it did not get many opportunities to broadcast live sports events played within Pakistan.

Nevertheless, on January 11th, 2012, PTV took another significant step by establishing a separate channel, which is totally dedicated for sports broadcasting. PTV Sports was started as a specialized 24/7 channel mostly based on the syndicated live international events, and acquirement of other such resource. The accompanying programming included pre and post-match analysis, and the channel immediately made its impact.

Literature Review

When we look at the term Broadcasting, then it is defined as a major portion of "mass communication," or else identified with the notion of mass media. Considering the Broadcasting concept in relation to the media; it means the dissemination of information with a larger audience. The broadcasting phenomenon originated when the message sharing through electrical means was made possible in the beginning of 1900s. With it, the traditional broadcasting sources emerged: the analogue radio and the analogue television. The radio gained popularity within public in the United States and Europe in the mid 1920s. It was this momentum which made broadcasting a public policy matter, and broadcasting from that onwards was considered a principal institution for access to education and entertainment (Munoz Tellez & Waitara, 2007).

The combination of sports along with the television became popular in 1947. The National Broadcasting Company (NBC), the American broadcast television network at that time broadcasted the World Series related to the New York Yankees and Brooklyn Dodgers. Later, in America in 1948, nearly 200000 televisions were there, and this is when the broadcasters planned to put money in the sports programming in order to increase the purchase of televisions. After that, it was in the middle of 1960s when the television networks saw an increase in sports content. Along with it, the advertisement with this specific content also increased; and from 1970 to 1985, the sports presented on the television became a great earning source. A significant example related to it is when the National

Football League (NFL) was broadcasted against \$50 million and the Major League Baseball (MLB) against \$18 million. This amount increased to \$450 million and \$160 million correspondingly in the 1985, which was also an evidence that coverage on technical terms was improving (Baran, 2011).

Then, emergence of the Entertainment and Sports Programming Network (ESPN) is considered a milestone in sports broadcasting history. It was the second dedicated sports channel after "SportsChannel," which went on air in 1977. The ESPN in September 1979 earlier became on air on cable television. Within the span of four years, the ESPN were seen within four million houses, and the number increased to four million in 1986. The ESPN in 2003 shifted to high definition transmission; and at present with the internet and the smart phones technology, the ESPN is televising 3D sports coverage available to these smart phones (Changnon, 2011).

It is important to mention that it was in 1998, when the Japan Broadcasting Corporation popularly known as NHK achieved a milestone through the development of 3D HDTV relay system. This technological development used a satellite in sharing the coverage of Nagano Winter Games to people in the Tokyo city. The live transmission of this nature through a terrestrial network and satellite was successfully performed during the 2002 FIFA World Cup soccer (Schreer et al., 2005).

Broadcasting sports content in the 3D format is unique due to the fact that stereo 3D experience is involved in it. For the purpose of live sports events using stereo broadcast technology, the several stereo camera rigs are employed together with the normal 2D cameras. Most importantly, there is a consistent ongoing research about the several camera arrangements for the renewal and representations of dynamic scenes (Hilton et al., 2011).

Apart from this, one cannot also undermine this fact that how the television industry has transformed has a direct impact on the sports coverage. It is the technology that is the driving force now, and the sports rights and the income resulting from it are now directly related to the technology factor (Noll, 2007).

The example of cricket sport is very important in context of sports broadcasting. The "Cricket and broadcasting" book written by Jack Williams highlights how the coverage of cricket sport grew from 1950 to 2004 through television; particularly with the arrival of a dedicated sports channel. The example of Sky Sports in this regard is extremely important. Also, Williams strongly believes that when compared with other sports, cricket has been watched more in Britain, for which he has presented interested figure from mid-1950s to the 1980s (Williams, 2011).

When we are discussing cricket in relation to sports broadcasting, one cannot forget the Australian media tycoon, Kerry Packer. Kerry Packer undoubtedly played a significant role in commercializing cricket. The 1977 World Series Cricket organized by Packer's Channel 9 changed the dynamics of sports

broadcasting, mainly due to tournament's innovative format and marketing plans. The use of colored cloths, floodlights for matches played at night, logos, drop-in pitches, cameras at both ends of the ground, microphones in the stumps etc; these were some incredible steps that began a new era in the sports coverage field (Mustafa, 2013).

If we look at some of the popular ball sports like soccer, basketball, cricket, baseball and tennis, in terms of broadcasting, it is a professional practice that the renowned sports channels are equipped with a specialized broadcasting team having a director and cameramen; and most significantly state-of-the-art technological equipment. It is important to understand that when it comes to broadcasting of sports matches, the director switches between cameras during the live match that requires proper training and experience (K. Choi et al., 2009).

The technological innovations in the broadcasting of sports events are very rapid. For instance, now the broadcasted matches contain virtual elements, which are there either for the advertisement purpose or it contains information. The information specifically is of diverse nature like the statistics of different players, the weather information, the technical aspects of any ground etc (Denia et al., 2011).

For this reason, the broadcasting rights deals in sports have become immensely important. As in Europe, football is a very popular sport. Looking at the media rights fees from the last decade and specifically taking the example of the FIFA World Cup, there is a massive increase that is around 900 percent; when compared from the last 20 years. Also, if we consider the English Premier League, there is an increase to 1000 percent in the broadcasting rights starting from its commencement time in 1992 (Hoehn & Kastrinaki, 2012).

In addition to it, this 21st century is considered the age of digital media, which has developed a demand culture for the sportsmen to remain constantly in touch with their fans; and this has given birth to new issues as well as new marketing benefits into the sports field. Now, the media especially the social media has influenced the sports very much, and there is an important debate that sports media has encouraged the norms related to capitalism, nationalism and racism (Kumar, 2018).

The advent of social media has greatly influenced the dynamics and consumption of sports. Contemporary researches with reference to the sports management have revealed that social media is playing a major part in shaping relationships between brands and individuals. At present, the social media content shared includes access behind the scenes, meetups of fans with athletes, new information, promotion etc (Filo et al., 2015).

Most importantly, the integration of digital media in the sports broadcasting field now holds strategic relevance in terms of a high-quality broadcaster of premium content. Equally significant right now is gaining subscribers and a specific share of viewers from the commercially relevant

audience. Also, the mobile phone technology and the internet are augmenting the sports experience of audience; as it is supplementing the television (Frandsen, 2012).

It is this emergence and rapid innovation in the digital media, which has also altered the production and reception of journalism. Especially, when it comes to production, the media workers now require new skills as their journalistic practices have become integrated with the digital media. It therefore, demands the media personnel to qualify for an active engagement with co-creating, co-producing audiences (Kroon & Eriksson, 2019).

Specifically, if we want to observe the impact of social media platforms then, Twitter provides us an excellent example about how different sports organizations and individual sportsmen use this platform for direct communication with their fans. Constant information and developments are being uploaded using this platform; and a reporter also tweet a short message about a story even before it is written (Hancherick, 2011).

There is another significant aspect that is related to the low-cost internet speed, which is considered a major factor behind the media-related consumer market having an influence on the sports field. The technology is now the driving force, which has transformed the earlier consumer environment in which the matches can be seen either within grounds or on Television (E. Y. Choi, 2022).

In addition to it, the hypercommercialized and hypermediated sports broadcasting environment of late capitalist sport, there is now varied positions of sport producers (athletes, coaches, managers, owners, and administrators) that co-create sporting events in conjunction with sport consumers (the ones who are attending the event). Due to this, the sport spectators are considered working customers that add to the surplus value of a sporting event (Andrews & Ritzer, 2018).

Apart from all these, the crews traveling and the production equipment transited between events; managing their cost itself is very demanding. However, with the innovation of the REMI (REMOte Integration) sports production technology, the cameras, microphones and cables are still traveling with the technical crew, but the actual control room including graphics and replay machines is staying and put in one or more broadcast production hub(s), where the production personnel can manage it all (Coche & Lynn, 2020).

Nevertheless, the circulation of capital within the sports fraternity in terms of broadcasting rights is undoubtedly defining the success of contemporary sports events. The example of the Indian Premier League (IPL) in cricket is of tremendous significance, since its television and digital broadcasting rights last year were sold for a record \$6.2 billion. The breakdown of this deal was one being the television rights for the Indian subcontinent, which Star India, the local Disney subsidiary, purchased for \$3.02 billion. The second is the digital rights, which

Viacom18, a joint venture between Paramount and India's Reliance Industries, bought for \$3.05 billion (Yasir, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

The Diffusion of Innovation and the Technological Determinism theories are employed to effectively analyze the findings of this study. First the Diffusion of Innovation theory holds relevance in this research because, it will support the examination about the standing of PTV Sports when it comes to the adoption of advance broadcasting technologies. Then, the Technological Determinism theory is also important with regard to this study, as it will help us establish whether the working personnel especially the top hierarchy at the PTV Sports are aware about the significance of employing advance technologies to their broadcasting setup.

Statement of the Problem

The diffusion of new technologies and the dynamic effects of convergence are altering the way that consumers view and perceive audio-visual content. As broadcasting services are continuously evolving, the television and broadcasting sector have been undergoing significant technological and structural changes, which have given consumers access even beyond their needs. However, Pakistan Television Corporation (PTV) have not been matching up its pace with the major technological and structural changes, occurring in television broadcasting sector all over the world. A great example of it is the PTV Sports, which on technological front lacks great innovation, when compared with some renowned sports television channels around the world.

Methodology

The Qualitative research approach is applied, for which television sports broadcasters, sports journalists and transmission engineers from the PTV, PTV Sports and private television channels in Pakistan are selected for study; from which in-depth interviews are conducted in relation to this research. For in-depth interviews, a total of twelve experts are selected. Among these twelve, six are from PTV and PTV Sports, and the remaining six are associated to private television channels in Pakistan, keeping in view the prerequisites of this study. The sampling list of in-depth interviewees is as follow:

R1: Dr. Nauman Niaz (Director Sports at PTV Sports), R2: Huma Sadaf (News Reporter/Producer at PTV), R3: Bilal Akram (TV Engineer at PTV), R4: Azeem Tahir Butt (TV Engineer at PTV), R5: Mian Saleem Hameed (Broadcast Engineering (EIC) in charge at PTV), R6: Mian Hassan Saleem (Producer Sports at PTV Sports), R7: Sohail Imran (Senior Correspondent Geo News), R8: Sana Ullah

Khan (Sports Journalist at Dunya TV), R9: Zainab Abbas (Sports Anchor/ Analyst at Dunya TV), R10: Afzaal Chaudhry (Editor Sports at Channel Five/ Anchor of sports program "Googly" at Channel Five), R11: Hafiz Muhammad Imran (Sports Reporter at Waqt News/ Anchor of sports program "Game Beat" at Waqt News) and R12: Ahmad Haseeb (Producer at City42).

Research Questions

RQ1: How the traditional mindset of PTV Sports in terms of opting advance broadcasting technologies can be analyzed?

RQ2: Is the top management at PTV Sports technologically conscious?

Results

The answers that exceptionally explained the RQ1 research question are given by R1 (Dr. Nauman Niaz), R5 (Mian Saleem Hameed) and R6 (Mian Hassan Saleem). The historical information of PTV and PTV Sports that R1 gave is just outstanding. He said that before answering this question in detail, I would first of all like to tell you what golden achievements PTV has achieved in sports broadcasting. PTV right from its start gave huge importance to sports coverage, which is visible from the fact that after few years of its launch, PTV took the initiative of broadcasting live sports events played in Pakistan. Despite Doordarshan, the Indian state television channel, covered cricket in bits and pieces by heavily showing recorded clips of England tour to India in 1951-1952. It was PTV that decided to seize the opportunity, as for the first time on Marylebone Cricket Club (MCC) tour to Pakistan in 1968 led by Sir Colin Cowdrey, PTV broadcasted the live portion of Test match at Lahore Gaddafi Stadium. Later, from 1972-1973 till 1996-1997, all international events played in Pakistan were broadcasted live by PTV. PTV's affection towards sports can also be traced from the fact that when PTV was launched on 26th November, 1964, at 5 past 4, Kanwal Naseer made the first announcement about a local women table tennis match. Therefore, sports was the first subject discussed on Pakistan state television channel. Further, from 1971-1972, PTV not only televised live cricket tournaments within the country, but also branded them by sponsoring the entire event. Hence, for the first time, the concept of TV and sports branding in the region was introduced by the PTV. In other words, the marketing of sports events was introduced as subject by the PTV. Then, PTV was the forerunner attracting the 1987 Reliance Cricket World Cup rights. Such was the situation that highly skilled PTV cameramen were employed by Doordarshan to cover the Indian portion of the tournament. PTV also broadcasted the first Hockey Champions Trophy in 1980, besides shown live the 1971 Hockey World Cup, 1972 Munich Olympics, 1976 Montreal Olympics, 1978 and 1982 Hockey World Cups. Also, the network

holds the distinction, having aired Olympics live from 1972 to 2012. Moreover, PTV has broadcasted live World Open Squash and all other international events held in Pakistan from 1972-1973 till 2009. In 1996-1997, sports broadcasting all over the world became commercial, and rights winner also started operating within the country. Such was the case in back to back cricket series against South Africa and West Indies, Star Sports acquired all physical and human resource support from PTV for broadcast of these two series. One should also remember that Ten Sports got their human resource mainly cameramen either directly from the PTV, or they were trained by the PTV. Despite being a state broadcaster and a government's body, PTV always had the best equipment and human resource until international sports connections were stopped on 3rd March, 2009, due to the attack on Sir Lanka cricket team bus in Lahore. Since 2009, PTV's broadcast equipment for sports has not been upgraded because of two major reasons:

- Upgradation is not cost effective.
- The sample size with regard to advertisement is small and does not correlate with investing money in upgradation, since no international event is being held in Pakistan due to the attack on Sir Lanka cricket team bus in Lahore on 3rd March, 2009.

Moving forward, PTV network acquired the rights of 2011 ICC Cricket World Cup for live televising of matches in Pakistan. PTV generated revenue of 930 million rupees from live broadcasting of these matches. However, PTV Home, the entertainment channel, and PTV News were used as airing vehicles for televising of these matches. Therefore, their own business was cannibalized. As a result, in December, 2011, it was decided to launch a specialized live event based sports channel named as "PTV Sports." After PTV Sports launch on January 11th, 2012, it has become the number one sports channel within Pakistan in terms of ratings, revenue generation and consumer demand, and it has successfully evolved as a brand as well. The 2015 ICC Cricket World Cup became the benchmark, as PTV Sports created history and became trendsetter by inviting legend ex-foreign cricket stars in Pakistan to create soft image of the country. Now, when we talk about the traditional mindset of PTV Sports in terms of opting advance broadcasting technologies, the R1 said that it is not the traditional mindset but other significant reasons that are halting the progress of PTV Sports. These reasons are as follow:

- Firstly, the human resource expenses currently in PTV are overwhelming, as the level of illegal hiring has reached up to 71% in the last couple of years. It has slowed down the growth of PTV as an organization, and like other segments of this organization, PTV Sports has also hugely suffered due to it for which the recent governments and top management at PTV deserves the blame.

- Secondly, it is important to understand that the dynamics of international sports broadcasting have totally changed. Technology at present is considered a central force in sports broadcasting, and understanding this fact famous sports channels like Sky Sports, Star Sports, Channel Nine etc, are now hugely equipped with latest equipment required for sports broadcasting. I proudly say that PTV Sports has tremendous Human Resource, but unfortunately our equipment does not match the standards of international sports broadcasting. For example, majority cameras of PTV Sports use 62x Zoom lenses, and we have only two cameras which are utilizing 82x Zoom lenses. You would be surprised to hear that most of the renowned international sports channels are operating with cameras that can easily utilize 100x Zoom lenses.
- Thirdly, again R1 mentioned the same above reason that the sample size with regard to advertisement is small and does not correlate with investing money in upgradation, since no international event is being held in Pakistan due to the attack on Sir Lanka cricket team bus in Lahore on 3rd March, 2009.

Then, R5 shared a great achievement of PTV in sports broadcasting. He said that the Grand Slam Sports Productions and PTV collaborated for the televising of 1996 Cricket World Cup matches played in Pakistan. I was the VTR engineer during televising of these matches, and along with my PTV support staff we beautifully conducted those matches. What I want to say is that PTV during coverage of popular sports events has proved their worth, and we are proud of it. In PTV Sports, the professional team from PTV who have huge experience in sports broadcasting are working remarkably well for success of this channel. However, it is a fact that for the adoption of advance broadcasting technologies you need massive funds, and the top management at PTV are very reluctant to provide them for these specific purposes. Hence, it would be wrong to say that the traditional mindset of PTV Sports is responsible for not opting advance broadcasting technologies. Further, R6 presented a different point of view, which is also very important to this study. He said that I proudly say that today what I have learnt about sports broadcasting, it is due to the sincere guidance of my seniors at PTV Sports. However, a fact that I want to highlight here is that there are many new youngsters who have recently joined PTV Sports, and are equipped with the latest knowledge of sports broadcasting. During work, when these youngsters present their innovative ideas to our seniors, some of them get offended as they feel it is disrespectful to their knowledge. That's why; I feel that in some way it is the old thinking pattern of our some seniors that create hurdle in adoption of advance broadcasting technologies.

These answers from R1, R5 and R6 are very important in context of this research, as majority of the people in Pakistan do not know what great feats PTV and later PTV Sports have achieved in sports broadcasting. After these significant facts shared by R1 and R5, it would really be wrong to say that the traditional mindset of PTV Sports in terms of opting advance broadcasting technologies is responsible for PTV Sports slow growth. It goes on to show that PTV has a great advantage of a fixed revenue source, and still they are going in loss is very

disappointing. Again, it is the corruption that has brought PTV to this disastrous stage the results of which are clearly visible in PTV Sports.

Moreover, one should not forget that the attack on Sir Lanka cricket team bus in Lahore on 3rd March, 2009, almost took all the international sports events to be played within Pakistan. Plus, during this whole decade, PTV also faced a set back as it did not get many opportunities to broadcast live sports events played within Pakistan. R1 perfectly explained this issue that the sample size with regard to advertisement is small and does not correlate with investing money in upgradation, since no international event is being held in Pakistan due to the attack on Sir Lanka cricket team bus in Lahore.

The answer from R6 is directly related to PTV Sports' organizational growth, which as earlier mentioned is on the slower side. When you hire professional people on merit, it overall creates a positive environment in an organization which easily allows seniors and juniors to collectively work for betterment of an organization, and hence, issues like these are automatically solved.

After that, the answers that very appropriately explained the RQ2 research question are given by R1 (Dr. Nauman Niaz), R6 (Mian Hassan Saleem) and R7 (Sohail Imran). R1 said that as far as the management of PTV Sports is concerned, definitely they are technologically conscious, and are absolutely willing to incorporate advance broadcasting technologies. However, we must not forget that PTV Sports is part of Pakistan Television Corporation (abbreviated as PTV). The top management of PTV is responsible for providing resources to PTV Sports, and R1 said that they have zero awareness about the significance of modern broadcasting equipment required for quality sports coverage. Hence, we are deprived of the funds needed to purchase this latest equipment. However, R6 made a very different and a valid point that the top hierarchy at PTV Sports despite having huge experience, also do not know much about what significance latest technology holds for quality sports coverage. We on and off brief them with plans as how we can bring latest broadcasting equipment to PTV Sports, but they do not give them the due attention it requires. After that, the answer given by R7 is also of great significance that Most of the people at top level in PTV Sports have been appointed on political grounds, and how can you expect them to be technologically conscious since they do not have a background of sports media industry.

In present-day sports broadcasting, it is very important that a sports channel should have a management that realizes how imperative it is to adopt advance broadcasting technologies required for quality sports coverage. It is essential that a point from R1 that he made in his previous RQ's answer should be repeated here. He said that it is important to understand that the dynamics of international sports broadcasting have totally changed. Technology at present is considered a central force in sports broadcasting, and understanding this fact famous sports channels like Sky Sports, Star Sports, Channel Nine etc, are now

hugely equipped with latest equipment required for sports broadcasting. R1 added that PTV Sports has tremendous Human Resource, but unfortunately our equipment does not match the standards of international sports broadcasting. For example, majority cameras of PTV Sports use 62x Zoom lenses, and we have only two cameras which are utilizing 82x Zoom lenses. You would be surprised to hear that most of the renowned international sports channels are operating with cameras that can easily utilize 100x Zoom lenses.

This whole point from R1 is a great proof that a technologically conscious management in a sports channel can only understand these crucial aspects for quality sports coverage. However, the opinions shared by R6 and R7 are also very important in context of this research question. What both of them are trying to say again reflects the organizational failures through which PTV is currently going through; corruption in the form of illegal hiring is a major reason for it. It is important to understand that some of the best people when are put in a corrupt setup, it in some way also effects their performance scale.

The Laggards point in the Diffusion of Innovation Theory perfectly explains the above answerers of interviewees. The Laggards point in this theory is about people who are bound by tradition and very conservative. They are very skeptical of change and are the hardest group to bring on board. This point is directly related to PTV's top management, as their zero technologically conscious behavior towards incorporation of modern broadcasting technologies for quality sports coverage, has severely affected PTV Sports' performance. Again, as mentioned earlier that corrupt practices and undue political interference in PTV have never allowed right people to be selected in PTV Sports, who have a proper sports media background.

If one wants to see a technologically conscious management in a sports channel, and how superbly they have adopted advance broadcasting technologies for quality sports coverage, then Sky Sports Cricket is a perfect example of it. The Technological Determinism Theory based on the thoughts of Marshall McLuhan should be considered in perspective of Sky Sports Cricket coverage. Marshall McLuhan believed that the new electronic media have completely changed the way people think, feel and act, and this theory is very appropriate in context of Sky Sports Cricket management. He envisaged that we would be in the midst of a revolution, and that the world will never be the same. The pictures below from Sky Sports Cricket coverage is a proof of it.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that PTV Sports have done a tremendous job to produce programs which are beautifully equipped with both entertainment and information. However, it is their adoption behavior towards advance broadcasting technologies that needed a critical examination. For this reason, a detail study was conducted to see the scale at which PTV Sports are adopting

advance broadcasting technologies, and whether the management at PTV Sports are technologically conscious or not.

The biggest finding of this research is the historical achievements which PTV has achieved in sports broadcasting, and sadly majority of people in Pakistan are unaware of that. It is this great legacy of PTV that has ultimately given birth to PTV Sports. Then, this study revealed that technology at present is considered a central force in sports broadcasting, and understanding this fact famous sports channels like Sky Sports, Star Sports, Channel Nine etc, are now hugely equipped with latest equipment required for sports broadcasting. PTV Sports has tremendous Human Resource, but unfortunately their equipment does not match the standards of international sports broadcasting, and hence requires upgradation. In addition to this, this research discussed that till early 2000, Pakistan was doing great in conducting of sports events, which later were reduced due to security reasons, and the attack on Sir Lanka cricket team bus in Lahore on 3rd March, 2009, almost took all the international sports events to be played within Pakistan. This directly affected the sports broadcasting space of Pakistan as our sports channels particularly PTV Sports are now deprived with the luxury of broadcasting and media rights for international and local sports events held within Pakistan.

Limitations and Future Recommendations

It has been just a decade to the PTV Sports' commencement, due to which there are no previous studies available on this sports channel. Moreover, the nature of this research topic is relatively new, and therefore, it is hard to find old studies related to this subject. As far as the future recommendations are concerned, a detail research on PTV Sports can be done on their programming setup. Apart from this, a study can be conducted on what scope the media industry of Pakistan provides for establishment of a sports channel, keeping in view the working of existing sports channels.

References

- Andrews, D. L., & Ritzer, G. (2018). Sport and prosumption. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 18(2), 356–373. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469540517747093>
- Changnon, S. A. (2011). *Live 3D Production of Sporting Events, The Future of Sports Broadcasting*. http://opensiuc.lib.siu.edu/gs_rp/162
- Choi, E. Y. (2022). The Mediating Role of Interaction Between Watching Motivation and Flow of Sports Broadcasting in Multi-Channel Network. *SAGE Open*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211068513>
- Choi, K., Lee, S. W., & Seo, Y. (2009). *AUTOMATIC BROADCAST VIDEO GENERATION FOR BALL SPORTS FROM MULTIPLE VIEWS*.
- Coche, R., & Lynn, B. J. (2020). Behind the scenes: COVID-19 consequences on broadcast sports production. *International Journal of Sport Communication*, 13(3), 484–493. <https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsc.2020-0231>
- Denia, A., Ribelles, J., & López And´oscarand´ And´oscar Belmonte, A. (2011). *Low Cost Virtual Animation Effects for Sports Broadcasting: Mosaics, Flags and Big-sized Flags*.
- Filo, K., Lock, D., & Karg, A. (2015). Sport and social media research: A review. In *Sport Management Review* (Vol. 18, Issue 2, pp. 166–181). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smr.2014.11.001>
- Frandsen, K. (2012). Sports broadcasting journalism and the challenge of new media. *Journal of Media and Communication Research*, 28, 5–21.
- Hancherick, D. (2011). *Tweet Talking: How Modern Technology and Social Media Are Changing Sports Communication*.
- Hilton, A., Guillemaut, J.-Y., Kilner, J., Grau, O., & Thomas, G. (2011). *3D-TV Production from Conventional Cameras for Sports Broadcast*. www.liberovision.com
- Hoehn, T., & Kastrinaki, Z. (2012). *BROADCASTING AND SPORT: VALUE DRIVERS OF TV RIGHT DEALS IN EUROPEAN FOOTBALL*.
- Kroon, Å., & Eriksson, G. (2019). The Impact of the Digital Transformation on Sports Journalism Talk Online. *Journalism Practice*, 13(7), 834–852. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2019.1577695>
- Kumar, M. (2018). Role of Media in Sports. ~ 135 ~ *International Journal of Physiology*, 3(1), 135–137. www.journalofsports.com
- Munoz Tellez, V., & Waitara, A. C. (2007). *A DEVELOPMENT ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED WIPO TREATY ON THE PROTECTION OF BROADCASTING AND CABLECASTING ORGANIZATIONS*.
- Mustafa, F. (2013). Cricket and globalization: Global processes and the imperial game. *Journal of Global History*, 8(2), 318–341. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1740022813000247>
- Nitin Kumar PGPCM, B. (2003). *Impact of sports/cricket on Television Broadcast industry in India*.
- Noll, R. G. (2007). *BROADCASTING AND TEAM SPORTS*.

Schreer, Oliver., Kauff, Peter., & Sikora, Thomas. (2005). *3D videocommunication : algorithms, concepts, and real-time systems in human centred communication*. Wiley.

Williams, J. (2011). *Cricket and broadcasting*. Manchester University Press.

Yasir, S. (2022, June 14). Indian Cricket Broadcast Rights Fetch a Record Price. *The New York Times*.